

Combinatorics another way - by addition

immediate

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Abstract

In this paper I show how to choose r objects from n , called ${}^n C_r$, by reducing the problem into smaller problems and just adding up the result. I first show that ${}^n C_r = \sum_{i=1}^{n-r+1} {}^{n-i} C_{r-1} = {}^{n-i} C_{r-1} + {}^{n-i} C_r$. Then using this equation I further show that ${}^n C_r = \sum_{j=1}^{n-r+1} K_{r-1,j} \times (n-r+2-j)$ where the coefficients $K_{i,j}$ come from a matrix \mathbf{K} with a very simple method to generate its entries. I then further show that ${}^n C_r = K_{n-r+1,r+1}$ which is a result attained just by simple addition with no multiplication involved. Using this method, I can then simply read off any desired ${}^n C_r$ by just looking up the corresponding entry in the \mathbf{K} matrix, which never changes. The attached Excel sheet, called *KMatrixCombinatorics*, implements this method. Finally, I discuss possible speed advantages of this method compared to the usual multiplication method.

1 Introduction

Once or twice a year, during long drives out of town, my dad sometimes tells a story, or asks a question, to keep my brother and I entertained. About 2-3 years ago he told me how to count the number of possible ways that n objects could be arranged. As usual I understood it then but forgot about it. Recently during another drive he reminded me and then told us an interesting story about a test question he got during his American SAT for college entrance:

"If 10 people in a room all shake hands with each other how many handshakes are there in total?"

My dad said he and my uncle, now in New York, solved it differently. My dad used multiplication but my uncle just counted. My dad said he thought that since each person has to shake hands with 9 other people,

that is $10 \cdot 9 = 90$ handshakes but double counted. Therefore there had to be $10 \cdot 9 / 2 = 45$ handshakes in total. He said my uncle solved it by breaking down the problem in the following simple manner: the 1st person shakes hands with the other 9, but when we come to the 2nd person we have to exclude the 1st person handshake as it is already included. Therefore the 2nd person shakes hands with the the remaining 8 and so on, with the 9th person shaking hands only with the 10th. This left my uncle with the result: $9 + 8 + 7 + \dots + 1 = 45$, which is the same as $10 \cdot 9 / 2$.

My dad also then explained to me that $10 \cdot 9 / 2 = {}^{10}C_2$ by showing how the general principle worked. So for example if we had to choose 3 objects out of 8, meaning 8C_3 , we have 8 choices for the first, 7 for the 2nd, and 6 for the 3rd. This gives $8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6$ possible ways of picking objects in order, but since we are choosing objects rather than arranging them we must remove all the additional counting. He then explained that since there were $3 \cdot 2 = 6$ ways of arranging the 3 objects chosen we have to divide $8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6$ by $3 \cdot 2$. This gave ${}^8C_3 = 8 \cdot 7 \cdot 6 / 3 \cdot 2$. It then immediately clear to me how to do this for any nC_r .

Next morning, while I was still half asleep in bed I found myself dreaming of this SAT problem of handshakes but involving 3 way handshakes instead of 2. Meaning 3 people shaking hands with each other at the same time. I know that for 10 people this would be ${}^{10}C_3 = 10 \cdot 9 \cdot 8 / 3 \cdot 2$, but I was dreaming of the counting method my uncle had used in the SAT. And then it just came to me even before I was fully awake: I just had to choose the first person, and then pair him up with any 2 of the remaining 9, then to exclude the first person, and then pair of the 2nd person with the remaining 8, all the way down to pairing the 8th person with the remaining 2 (the 9th and 10th). And then it became clear to me that I was just choosing 2 people every time from a smaller group of people. So it was clear that

$${}^{10}C_3 = {}^9C_2 + {}^8C_2 + {}^7C_2 + \dots + {}^2C_2 \quad (1)$$

I got up and checked this by using it against the multiplication method and got 120 as answer by both methods. I then checked this for other combinations and it always worked as I expected it to. At this point I realised that the 9C_2 terms etc on the right side could be further broken down into 8C_1 and other terms involving just 1 choice. This meant that I can write

$${}^9C_2 + {}^8C_2 + \dots + {}^2C_2 = ({}^8C_1 + \dots + {}^1C_1) + ({}^7C_1 + \dots + {}^1C_1) + \dots + 1 \quad (2)$$

Now as ${}^nC_1 = n$, I had very simple additions involving integers 8 all the way down to 1. For ease of display here I write ${}^nC_1 = n = n_1$, giving us

$${}^{10}C_3 = 1 \times 8_1 + 2 \times 7_1 + 3 \times 6_1 + 4 \times 5_1 + 5 \times 4_1 + 6 \times 3_1 + 7 \times 2_1 + 8 \times 1_1 \quad (3)$$

So it became clear to me that I had coefficients 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 multiplying the n_1 terms respectively in this case. I realised I could do this for any ${}^n C_r$ long as I was able to find the correct coefficients. The next section shows how to do this.

2 General r-way Handshakes

In the previous section I showed how to calculate choices for 3 way handshakes. Here I want to show how to calculate r-way handshakes, which I will first motivate by an example for a 4-way handshake. This is to show how to find a general method to find the coefficients.

2.1 Example ${}^9 C_4$:

We know that

$${}^9 C_4 = {}^8 C_3 + {}^7 C_3 + {}^6 C_3 + {}^5 C_3 + {}^4 C_3 + {}^3 C_3 \quad (4)$$

which we know can be broken down further in successive steps

$$\begin{aligned} {}^8 C_3 &= {}^7 C_2 + {}^6 C_2 + {}^5 C_2 + {}^4 C_2 + {}^3 C_2 + {}^2 C_2 \\ {}^7 C_3 &= {}^6 C_2 + {}^5 C_2 + {}^4 C_2 + {}^3 C_2 + {}^2 C_2 \\ {}^6 C_3 &= {}^5 C_2 + {}^4 C_2 + {}^3 C_2 + {}^2 C_2 \\ {}^5 C_3 &= {}^4 C_2 + {}^3 C_2 + {}^2 C_2 \\ {}^4 C_3 &= {}^3 C_2 + {}^2 C_2 \\ {}^3 C_3 &= {}^2 C_2 \end{aligned}$$

$${}^9 C_4 = 1 \times ({}^7 C_2) + 2 \times ({}^6 C_2) + 3 \times ({}^5 C_2) + 4 \times ({}^4 C_2) + 5 \times ({}^3 C_2) + 6 \times ({}^2 C_2) \quad (5)$$

But right hand side can be further reduced, leading to

$${}^9 C_4 = 1 \times ({}^6 C_1) + 3 \times ({}^5 C_1) + 6 \times ({}^4 C_1) + 10 \times ({}^3 C_1) + 15 \times ({}^2 C_1) + 21 \times ({}^1 C_1) \quad (6)$$

So now we have coefficients 1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21 multiplying the n_1 terms respectively for this case.

2.2 The Combinatorics Matrix K

By using, the above examples, and writing out coefficients out for different choices of ${}^n C_r$, I was able to generate the following matrix, which I call **K**:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{1,1} & K_{1,2} & K_{1,3} & K_{1,4} & K_{1,5} \cdots \\ K_{2,1} & K_{2,2} & K_{2,3} & K_{2,4} & K_{2,5} \cdots \\ K_{3,1} & K_{3,2} & K_{3,3} & K_{3,4} & K_{3,5} \cdots \\ K_{4,1} & K_{4,2} & K_{4,3} & K_{4,4} & K_{4,5} \cdots \\ K_{5,1} & K_{5,2} & K_{5,3} & K_{5,4} & K_{5,5} \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \cdots \\ 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 & 5 \cdots \\ 1 & 3 & 6 & 10 & 15 \cdots \\ 1 & 4 & 10 & 20 & 35 \cdots \\ 1 & 5 & 15 & 35 & 70 \cdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

If we look at this it is easy to see

$$K_{1,j} = 1, \forall j \quad (8)$$

$$K_{2,j} = \sum_{l=1}^j K_{1,l} \quad (9)$$

$$K_{i,j} = \sum_{l=1}^j K_{i-1,l} \quad (10)$$

$$K_{i,j} = K_{i,j-1} + K_{i-1,j} \quad (11)$$

3 The General Result for ${}^n C_r$

Now using the above, I can write the general result

$${}^n C_r = \sum_{i=1}^{n-r+1} {}^{n-i} C_{r-1} = {}^{n-i} C_{r-1} + {}^{n-i} C_r \quad (12)$$

in terms of the elements of the matrix \mathbf{K}

$${}^n C_r = \sum_{j=1}^{n-r+1} K_{r-1,j} ({}^{n-r+2-j} C_1) \quad (13)$$

Since we know what ${}^{n-r+2-j} C_1 = n - r + 2 - j$, we have

$${}^n C_r = \sum_{j=1}^{n-r+1} K_{r-1,j} (n - r + 2 - j) \quad (14)$$

After, reaching this result, I set up the spreadsheet, and checked different combinations. While looking at the spreadsheet I noticed that

$${}^n C_r = K_{n-r+1,r+1} \quad (15)$$

which I find a very remarkable result because it is just based on generating a very simple matrix by addition.

I will now explain why ${}^n C_r = K_{n-r+1,r+1}$ works as well as it does. Please first note that the matrix \mathbf{K} can be written with entries in the ${}^n C_r$ format :

K_matrix	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
3	1	3	6	10	15	21	28	36	45	55	66
4	1	4	10	20	35	56	84	120	165	220	286
5	1	5	15	35	70	126	210	330	495	715	1,001
6	1	6	21	56	126	252	462	792	1,287	2,002	3,003
7	1	7	28	84	210	462	924	1,716	3,003	5,005	8,008
8	1	8	36	120	330	792	1,716	3,432	6,435	11,440	19,448
9	1	9	45	165	495	1,287	3,003	6,435	12,870	24,310	43,758
10	1	10	55	220	715	2,002	5,005	11,440	24,310	48,620	92,378
11	1	11	66	286	1,001	3,003	8,008	19,448	43,758	92,378	184,756
12	1	12	78	364	1,365	4,368	12,376	31,824	75,582	167,960	352,716
13	1	13	91	455	1,820	6,188	18,564	50,388	125,970	293,930	646,546
14	1	14	105	560	2,380	8,568	27,132	77,520	203,490	497,420	1,144,066
15	1	15	120	680	3,060	11,628	38,760	116,280	319,770	817,190	1,961,256
16	1	16	136	816	3,876	15,504	51,264	170,544	490,314	1,307,504	3,368,760
17	1	17	153	969	4,845	20,349	74,613	245,157	735,471	2,042,975	5,311,735
18	1	18	171	1,140	5,985	26,334	100,947	346,104	1,081,575	3,124,550	8,436,285
19	1	19	190	1,350	7,315	33,649	134,596	480,700	1,582,275	4,686,825	13,123,110
20	1	20	210	1,560	8,855	42,504	177,100	657,800	2,220,075	6,096,900	20,030,010

Figure 1: The Combinatorics Matrix \mathbf{K} with the first 20 rows and 11 columns

$$\begin{bmatrix}
 {}^0C_0 & {}^1C_0 & {}^2C_0 & {}^3C_0 \dots \\
 {}^1C_1 & {}^2C_1 & {}^3C_1 & {}^4C_1 \dots \\
 {}^2C_2 & {}^3C_2 & {}^4C_2 & {}^5C_2 \dots \\
 {}^3C_3 & {}^4C_3 & {}^5C_3 & {}^6C_3 \dots \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots
 \end{bmatrix}
 =
 \begin{bmatrix}
 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \dots \\
 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \dots \\
 1 & 3 & 6 & 10 \dots \\
 1 & 4 & 10 & 20 \dots \\
 \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots
 \end{bmatrix}
 \quad (16)$$

In this format it becomes obvious that the r -th row represents all the ${}^nC_{r-1}$ elements starting with $n = r - 1$. Now recall equation (10) and equation (11). Equation (10) says that the $K_{i,j}$ element is the sum of all elements in the $i - 1$ row from the 1st column to the j -th. We see this is true because of the decomposition in Equation (12). Equation (10) also shows that $K_{i,j}$ is the sum of the $K_{i-1,j}$ and $K_{i,j-1}$ elements. So now we see that $K_{i,j}$ represent ${}^jC_{i-1}$ entries. So for example for the entry 5C_3 the element to left is 4C_3 and the element above would be 4C_2 . From equation (11) and by checking values we can see that this is clearly true. ${}^5C_3 = {}^4C_3 + {}^4C_2 = 4 + 6 = 10$.

4 Discussion and further research

It seems to me the method in this paper is much easier than multiplying lots of numbers together. In fact, if I had to calculate lots of different combinations of choices, creating the simple matrix above just once is enough. I plan to write Python code to compare the speed of this method versus the multiplication (factorial) method.